

Phase-Controlled, Speckle-Free Holographic Projection with Applications in Precision Optogenetics

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ABSTRACT

Holographic speckle is a major impediment to computer generated holographic (CGH) projections in applications ranging from display, optical tweezers and machining to optogenetic neural control. We present a new iterative phase retrieval algorithm that allows the projection of amplitude-controlled speckle-free one-dimensional patterns with a high degree of pattern uniformity. The algorithm, termed the Weighted Gerchberg-Saxton with Phase-Control (GSW-PC), is shown to have the ability to simultaneously control both the phase and amplitude of projected patterns with high diffraction efficiencies. Furthermore, we show that the new framework can address the challenge of projecting volumetric phase and amplitude controlled patterns, by incorporating GSW-PC with the angular spectrum method. The algorithms performance is numerically and experimentally tested, and further compared to conventional and modern CGH techniques.

Introduction

Optogenetics has become a central tool in Neuroscience research¹. The ability to remotely stimulate cells with cell-type selectivity and high spatial and temporal resolutions² provides major advantages over earlier experimental perturbation methods such as electrical stimulation. Optogenetic tools are currently also being developed for applications ranging from vision restoration devices to implantable brain interfaces³⁻⁵. Interestingly, Computer Generated Holographic (CGH) projection systems have emerged as a particularly attractive option for delivering precisely targeted light to optogenetically transduced cells^{3,6-8}, and specifically for the simultaneous stimulation of multiple cells. CGH uses phase-only Spatial Light Modulators (SLMs) for spatially adjusting the wavefront's phases⁹, and a lens, which under Fraunhofer diffraction conditions reconstructs a Fourier transform (FT) of the wavefront. The wavefront's FT is projected onto the optogenetically transduced cells, allowing high rate dynamic generation of distributed patterns for neural stimulation. The use of such holographic optical neural interfaces (HONIs) for photo-stimulation offers substantial benefits over alternative amplitude modulation approaches in terms of power efficiency and maximal irradiance, and ultimately enables safer designs¹⁰; for multi-photon stimulation and imaging light efficiency is crucial and HONIs have emerged as the key enabling solution.

Since SLMs only modulate the input beam's phases, CGH requires phase retrieval algorithms for calculating the appropriate phase image to project, based on its target FT reconstruction. For HONIs and many other applications, it is important that the projected pattern will be diffraction efficient, smooth and uniform. However, conventional iterative CGH algorithms, like the Gerchberg-Saxton (GS) algorithm and its common derivatives^{11,12}, only constrain the modulus of the projected pattern, allowing its phases to vary randomly. The weighted GS algorithm (GSW) for example, reaches near perfect modulus uniformities and high efficiencies by introducing weights into the projected domain's constraints, but lacks any phase control. These random phases lead to holographic speckles, a phenomenon that arises from the projection of contiguous patterns with varying phases: the spots can interact destructively, which causes high contrast regions to appear in the projected pattern¹³ (illustrated in Fig. 1.a). Several time averaging solutions to the holographic speckle problem were proposed¹⁴⁻¹⁶ and shown to provide a reduction of speckle contrast in one and two-photon holographic projections. However, time averaging requires the projection of multiple holograms to reduce speckle noise, thereby sacrificing the temporal resolution.

Alternative approaches to speckle reduction are based on jointly controlling both the amplitude and phase of the projected patterns (Fig. 1.a), an attribute that has multiple alternative motivations. Physical schemes for realizing this

through controlled spatial modulation of the hologram's phase and amplitudes were developed^{17,18}, but require strict alignment and calibration of the optical components. Algorithmic solutions that achieve phase and modulus control are a possible alternative. Early attempts at speckle reduction focused on applying phase-smoothing constraints in the projected plane^{19,20}, but require over-sampling of the pattern, and post-iterations with reduced phase freedom, thus increasing the computational load by orders of magnitude. Another potential approach for achieving phase control is to divide the projected plane into constrained and constraint-free regions²¹, but this results in low efficiencies and uniformities in Fourier based holographic systems. An important recent contribution^{22,23} addresses this challenge by incorporating phase information into the GS-type iteration process. However, these algorithms do not explicitly maximize the accuracy of the pattern moduli, and require to manually set a predefined rate parameter that affects the diffraction efficiency. Here, we introduce a new method for modulus *and* phase control of projected patterns, which allows projection of speckle-free patterns with high diffraction efficiency. The algorithm performs well given arbitrary 1-dimensional (1D) patterns, with no need for pattern-specific parameter adjustment.

Gerchberg-Saxton with Phase Control (GSW-PC)

Algorithm Description

As schematically illustrated in Fig. 1.b, GSW-PC follows the general procedure of the GSW algorithm¹², using dual FTs between the projected image domain (V), and the hologram domain (H), to satisfy each domain's constraint in each iteration, and incorporating a set of weights (W) to iteratively correct the pattern moduli in V . However, in GSW the projected domain constraints are solely on the modulus of the projected pattern ($|V_{init}|$) while individual pattern phases are randomized to promote convergence. To enforce phase control, GSW-PC adds an additional constraint ($\angle V_{init}$) on the phases of the projected pattern (Eq. (2)). This step uses a solution suggested by Yuan and Tao²², where the non-pattern (background) pixels of the projected image aren't set to zero modulus and preserve their phase information between iterations. Following Ref. 22, a control parameter (δ) adjusts how much relative intensity is deflected towards the projected pattern vs. the background. Importantly, in GSW-PC, this parameter is allowed to decrease iteratively based on the current pattern uniformity levels in each iteration (see Eqs. (7-10)); This maximizes pattern efficiency and provides image-independent parameter optimization. The algorithm implements the following domain constraints:

1. Hologram domain constraints:

$$H = \exp(i \cdot \angle H^-) \quad (1)$$

2. Projected domain constraints:

$$V = W^k \circ \exp(i \cdot \angle V_{init}^-) + \delta^k \cdot (J - |V_{init}|) \circ \exp(i \cdot \angle V^-) \quad (2)$$

With the weights calculated using:

$$\begin{aligned} W^0 &= J \\ W^k &= W^{k-1} \circ \left| \hat{V}_{init}^- \right| ./ \left| \hat{V}^- \right| \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where J is a matrix of ones, $X \circ Y$ is a Hadamard product, $X./Y$ is an element wise division, k is the iteration number and $|\hat{V}|$ means that the modulus of V was normalized to have a maximum value of 1 as so $|\hat{V}| = |V|/\max(|V|)$.

3D Light Shaping Using the Angular Spectrum Method

Multiplane projection is likely to have an important role in Optogenetics for simultaneous stimulation of multiple cells dispersed over a 3D volume, as well as for optimizing individual cells stimulation by projecting 3D patterns that wrap around each cell's membrane and thus activate a large number of photo-sensitive channels (illustrated in Fig. 2.a), which adds an additional challenge to the phase retrieval problem. The angular spectrum method (ASM) is an approach used for modeling the propagation of a wave field in free space, based on scalar diffraction theory. The method uses Fast FTs to decompose an

optical wavefront into multiple plane waves with different spatial frequencies, and to superimpose them in the propagated plane. The general algorithm for the ASM is as follows

$$V_{propagated} = IFFT [FFT (V) \circ H] \quad (4)$$

where H is the transfer function of the angular spectrum, and can be expressed as:

$$H(u, v) = \exp \left\{ j k z \left[1 - (\lambda u)^2 - (\lambda v)^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \right\} \quad (5)$$

where, z is the propagation distance, λ is the projected wavelength, $k = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda}$ is the wavenumber and u, v are the spatial frequencies.

To implement GSW-PC based 3D projection we followed the general approach described by Wu *et al.*²³ (see Fig. 2.b). The iteration process starts with projection of the hologram to the projected Fourier plane (i.e. the lens focal plane) using a FFT (step 1). The projected wavefront is then propagated from the Fourier plane to the other axially-shifted planes using the ASM (step 2), where the constraints of the individual planes are applied on the wavefield. The wavefield of every plane is then propagated back to the Fourier plane using the ASM (step 3), and subsequently propagated backward to the hologram plane using an IFFT (step 4). The phases of the wavefields are eventually summed, and the process repeats until a quality criterion is met. This process outputs a two-dimensional hologram that produces three dimensional structures in its projected domain.

Performance Measures

The following quality measures were used to determine the performance of the algorithm (adapted from Ref. 12):

Diffraction efficiency

$$H(u, v) = \exp \left\{ j k z \left[1 - (\lambda u)^2 - (\lambda v)^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \right\} \quad (6)$$

Uniformity measures (in the case of constant modulus and phase projections)

$$mod. \text{ uniformity} = 1 - \frac{\max \{ |I_p| \} - \min \{ |I_p| \}}{\max \{ |I_p| \} + \min \{ |I_p| \}} \quad (7)$$

$$pahse \text{ uniformity} = 1 - \frac{\max \{ \angle V_p + \pi \} - \min \{ \angle V_p + \pi \}}{\max \{ \angle V_p + \pi \} + \min \{ \angle V_p + \pi \}} \quad (8)$$

where p is the index of projected pattern, i is the image index and $I = |V|^2$ is the energy flux.

In the case of projection of non-constant patterns, we used instead normalized mean squared error (NMSE) measures of the phase and amplitude difference between the projected pattern and the target pattern. As defined in Eqs. (9-10), the MSEs were normalized by dividing them by the maximal possible MSE value for the given patterns, allowing us as to set nominal generalized uniformity values needed to update δ irrespective of the input pattern.

$$Mod.NMSE = 1 - \frac{Mod.MSE}{Mod.MSE_{max}} = 1 - \frac{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{p=1}^n (|\hat{V}_p^-| - |\hat{V}_{init_p}|)^2}{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{p=1}^n (\max\{|\hat{V}_{init_p}|, 1 - |\hat{V}_{init_p}|\})^2} \quad (9)$$

$$Phase NMSE = 1 - \frac{Phase MSE}{Phase MSE_{max}} = 1 - \frac{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{p=1}^n (\angle \hat{V}_p^- - \angle \hat{V}_{init_p})^2}{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{p=1}^n \pi^2} \quad (10)$$

Numerical Results

The following subsections show numerical simulation results examining GSW-PC performance in different core scenarios (algorithms were implemented in Matlab).

Uniform-intensity Patterns

Figure 3 shows the process of optimizing the different performance measures during the iterations of the GSW-PC algorithm for different input images. During the pre-adaptation period, the δ value is high (initially set to 0.1), allowing the algorithm to rapidly converge to almost perfect modulus and phase uniformities, but with a suboptimal efficiency. After these high uniformities are reached, adaptation commences and δ begins to decrease (by a factor of 0.9 each step), causing the efficiency to rise; δ continues to decrease until the uniformity drops, wherein the iteration process is stopped.

Next, we compared the new algorithm to related alternatives including: (1) a non-adaptive (constant δ) version of GSW-PC, (2) GSW and (3) Yuan & Tao's 'phase and amplitude' algorithm²² (referred to as YT). The comparative results (Fig. 4) show that, as expected, GSW, which has no control over the projected pattern's phases, leads to null phase uniformity, whereas YT achieves good phase uniformity and efficiency, but low modulus uniformity. By adjusting the pattern weights, the non-adaptive GSW-PC dramatically improves the modulus uniformity compared to YT. Finally, the complete GSW-PC (adaptive) algorithm, reaches high phase and modulus uniformities and optimal efficiency adapted to each given input 1D pattern.

Non-uniform Patterns

Projection of non-uniform patterns is an important feature in many applications - e.g. in optogenetics it can be used for compensating for non-uniformities caused by variable expression levels of the photo-sensitive channels as well as by the inherent non-uniformity of the projection system³. Figure 5 shows results achieved with the GSW-PC method in projecting patterns that are non-uniform in both intensity and phase: amplitude and phase non-uniformities were introduced through V_{init} . The results clearly indicate that even in this more challenging scenario, the new method is generally able to combine very high pattern controllability with high efficiencies (approaching 50%).

3D Holography

Figure 6 shows results of testing the multi-layer CGH capability of the 3D GSW-PC algorithm, by projecting 3D pattern of rings with varying diameters. This pattern can be designed to match the membrane's geometry for efficient multi-photon optogenetic stimulation of single cells. The adjacent rings were calculated at a distance of $z = 2\mu m$ from each other, with a projected wavelength of $\lambda = 920nm$. The performance measures results for each plane show that the solution reaches near perfect phase and modulus uniformities, with efficiencies that are relatively high for multiple layer projection. In comparison, generating the same 3D pattern using the algorithm presented in Ref. 23, led to a highly non-uniform pattern (< 70% modulus uniformity values for generally similar efficiencies, results not shown).

Experimental Results

A two-photon holographic projection system (Fig. 7.a) was used to test the performance of the GSW-PC algorithm. An expanded beam from an ultrafast Titanium-Sapphire laser (MaiTai WB, Spectra-Physics, set to $\lambda = 920nm$) had its polarization rotated using a $\lambda/2$ waveplate, before hitting a phase SLM (XY Phase, Boulder Nonlinear Systems) and a Fourier lens. The

zero-order spot was blocked in the projection plane which was imaged through a custom microscope (objective: 40×, 0.8NA, Apo NIR; Nikon) onto a sample containing a Fluorescein solution. The two-photon excited fluorescence image was captured using a CCD camera (GC1380H, Prosilica).

We used the system to project holograms calculated using GSW and GSW-PC for multiple different patterns (circles, curved lines and spirals). As can be clearly seen in Fig. 7.b, images obtained using GSW are strongly speckle contaminated, whereas the GSW-PC patterns do not exhibit this phenomenon. Quantitatively, the GSW patterns had 50–100% higher speckle contrast²⁴ than the corresponding GSW-PC projections (Fig. 7.c, using the following measure for contrast:

$$contrast = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{std(p_i)}{mean(p_i)} \quad (11)$$

where the pattern is divided into n regions (p_i) to cancel out variations due to the non-uniform illumination and detection by the optical system. We note that the contrast estimate does not fully capture the contrast improvement due to partial volume effect caused by limited resolution of the CCD camera.

Discussion

We have presented a new CGH method for controlling both the phase and amplitude of the projected pattern. The new GSW-PC algorithm allows projection of arbitrary 1-D patterns with high efficiency and uniformities, and thus provides speckle free projections using a single hologram in either 2D or 3D (e.g., using the ASM adaptation). The algorithm was tested with a 2P projection system, and demonstrated a marked reduction of speckle contrast compared to the GSW method, at the cost of only a moderate increase in computational load (calculation of the quality measures in each iteration, and some extra iterations for algorithm convergence).

We anticipate that GSW-PC will provide significant benefits for a variety of CGH applications, due to different aspects of its ability to allow uniquely precise and flexible control over properties of the projected patterns. Rendering the patterns to be speckle-free does not only allow for more highly controlled and smooth stimulation intensity profiles, but also avoids 'hot spots' where intensities could be high enough to cause bleaching, membrane poration²⁵ or other forms of tissue-damage, which collectively may lead to less reproducible results during extended precision optogenetic stimulation experiments. Avoiding laser speckle is also highly desirable and has been intensely researched in holographic laser machining, processing and polymerization^{26–28} and in holographic 3D display systems^{29,30}. Furthermore, GSW-PCs ability to directly and flexibly control the pattern's phase could be used in optical tweezers setups for manipulating particles along arbitrarily shaped phase ramped 1D patterns^{18,21} (optionally together with flexible amplitude variations).

One noted limitation of the proposed approach is its ability to generate only one-dimensional projection patterns (i.e., curved lines, rings, spirals, etc.) with high efficiencies. To directly examine this issue, we evaluated the different performance measures as a function of the projected pattern width (see Fig. 8.a), finding that efficiency drops very strongly with pattern width. A similar drop in efficiency was observed for the projection of straight lines (not shown). We believe that the lack of randomness in the projected pattern's phase is the cause for this behavior due to inherent properties of the complex FT, which decomposes a complex image with randomized phase into a relatively uniformly distributed wide range of frequencies. This allows algorithms such as the GSW to converge to high efficiencies when imposing a uniform modulus in the hologram domain. On the other hand, a complex image with regions of constant phase, is decomposed by the FT into a non-uniform distribution of frequencies, with high energy residing in its low frequencies. This non-uniform distribution prevents the GSW-PC algorithm from converging to high efficiencies when projecting two-dimensional constant phase patterns. Nevertheless, Fig. 8.b shows that regardless of the efficiency, 2D wide patterns projected with the GSW-PC algorithm continue to display speckle-free results, compared to patterns projected with the GSW algorithm, due to high uniformities level conservation (see Fig. 8.a).

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Acknowledgements

The research was financially supported by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under ERC grant agreement 648927, and by the U.S National Institutes of Health (award Number 1U01NS090498-01).

Author contributions statement

T.A developed the concept, performed the numerical simulations and carried out the experiments. T.A and S.S contributed to writing and finalizing the paper. S.S supervised the project.

Additional information

Competing financial interests The authors declare no competing financial interests.

Figure 1. GSW with Phase-Control. a) Illustrated holographic stimulation of multiple neurons simultaneously: in a speckle free pattern (middle) phase uniformity is high, leading to low speckle contrast, while a low phase uniformity pattern exhibits holographic speckles and high speckle contrast (right panel). The phase graphs represent pixel numbers along the spirals. b) 2D GSW-PC hologram computation process. H and H^- are the constrained and unconstrained hologram respectively, V and V^- are the constrained and unconstrained projected image respectively, while $V_{background}$ is the unconstrained background of the projected image, V_{init} is the target projected pattern, W are weights used to adjust the projected modulus, and δ is the background intensity control parameter.

Figure 2. 3D holographic projection. a) 3D stimulation can be used to target multiple cells distributed at different depths using a single projection (left) and/or stimulate individual cells using multiple rings projected at different depths, thus maximizing the coverage of the light sensitive channels (right). b) Implementation schematic of the 3D GSW-PC iteration process.

Figure 3. GSW-PC performance and convergence characteristics. a,b) target images. c,d) performance measures. e,f) δ adaptation. In the pre-adaptation period δ is held constant, but is allowed to decrease after high uniformities are reached (adaptation range), leading to a corresponding increase in efficiency.

Figure 4. Performance and convergence characteristics comparison between GSW-PC, GSW-PC Non-Adaptive, YT and GSW methods. Target patterns: a) spiral b) Lena image filtered by Canny edge detector.

Figure 5. GSW-PC performance and convergence characteristics for a non-uniform target pattern. a) Resulting phase and modulus images for a multi-spiral projection pattern with different moduli and phase. b) Performance measures. c) Controllability of the individual spiral intensities achieved using the proposed method. The lower amplitude spirals had higher variability.

Figure 6. Projection of speckle-free 3D holograms using GSW-PC ASM. a) Performance measures in each of the projected planes. b) Target pattern consisting of 3-rings distant $z = 2\mu\text{m}$ from each other.

Figure 7. Experimental evaluation of GSW-PC. a) Illustration of the 2P projection system. b) Patterns projected using the 2P projection system captured using the CCD, left images are results of the GSW algorithm, right images are results of the GSW-PC algorithm; scale bar = $25\mu\text{m}$. c) Speckle contrast comparison.

Figure 8. Effect of 2D target pattern characteristics on GSW-PC's performance. a) Left: performance measures vs. width of projected ring pattern: the efficiency decreases as width increases while uniformity measures remain high; Right: projected ring pattern. b) Patterns projected using the 2P projection system, comparing GSW (top) with GSW-PC (bottom) algorithm; notice that GSW-PC provides uniform speckle-free projections irrespective of pattern width; scale bar = $25\mu m$.